

Source: Zavarian, A. A., Arman, A., Ghotbi, S. M. J., Korpi, A. G., Salehi, M., Mardani, M. Hafezi, F., [Shafiekhani, A.](#), Tălu, S., Afghan, A. S. (2018). Behaviors of capacitive and Pirani vacuum gauges: Case study on time effect. *Vakuum in Forschung und Praxis*, 30(5), 39-44. <https://doi.org/10.1002/vipr.201800693>

Behaviors of capacitive and Pirani vacuum gauges: Case study on time effect

Ali Asghar Zavarian, Ali Arman, S. M. Jamal Ghotbi, Alireza Grayeli Korpi, Maryam Salehi, Mohsen Mardani, Fatemeh Hafezi, [Azizollah Shafiekhani](#), Ștefan Tălu, Ashkan Sepehr Afghan

[Azizollah Shafiekhani](#): Department of Physics, Faculty of Physics and Chemistry, Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Knowing the exact pressure of the process has a great impact on the validity of the results, product quality, energy efficiency, and in some processes, on the security of work with the system. Hence, the calibration of the barometers and the accuracy of the readings should be taken seriously. Choosing the appropriate time interval for re-calibration is done according to the extent and conditions of use, uncertainty, and the inaccuracy allowed in measurement, constructive suggestion, and some other things. Failure to pay attention to the importance of periodic calibration in vacuum gauges leads to some irreparable losses in the research project and the vacuum generator system. In this study, using McLeod's barometer, the deviation of capacitive and Pirani vacuum gauges is investigated at different time intervals in the middle vacuum range, and it is determined that the vacuum gauge faces a serious deviation from the actual calibrated amount for upper and lower ranges of middle vacuum in the same working pressure range over time.